

Addition Complexes of Dialkyl Phosphonates with Tin(IV) and Organotin(IV) Chlorides

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Addition complexes of dialkyl phosphonates with tin(IV) chloride, diorganotin dichloride and triorganotin chloride have been prepared and characterised on the basis of ir and nmr (^1H , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn) spectral data. Dialkyl phosphonates are bound to the metal atom via the phosphoryl (P=O) oxygen and the effectiveness of coordination depends upon the donor strength of the ligand and the environment of the central tin atom.

IN continuation of our investigations on the dialkyl phosphonate and dialkyl thiophosphonate¹ derivatives of tin (IV) and arsenic(III)², it was of interest to make a detailed study of the reaction of tin(IV) and organotin(IV) chlorides with dialkyl phosphonates.

Experimental

Dialkyl phosphonates were synthesised by the reported methods³. Tin tetrachloride and organotin chlorides were distilled before use. Solvents were dried by established methods.

Preparation of addition complexes: Considerable heat was evolved on mixing tin tetrachloride and organotin chlorides with dialkyl phosphonates. Hence, preparation of the complexes was carried out by mixing the reactants in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios using n-hexane as solvent at 0–5° with constant stirring. The mixture was then kept overnight at ambient temperature. As the addition complexes formed were immiscible with n-hexane, the products were obtained by decanting the upper layer of n-hexane. The compounds were purified by washing with n-hexane and dried under reduced pressure.

Tin was estimated as SnO_2 by decomposing the compound in a mixture of $\text{HNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (A. R.) and precipitating it as $\text{SnO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the gradual addition of liquid ammonia followed by igniting it as SnO_2 . Chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. Results are stated in Table 1.

Ir spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra ($\text{CCl}_4/\text{CDCl}_3$) on a Perkin-Elmer R12-B spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 900 spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

The following addition complexes of tin tetrachloride and organotin chlorides with dialkyl

phosphonates have been isolated: (i) $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$, where $\text{R}=\text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Pr}^n, \text{Pr}^i$; (ii) $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot (\text{R}'\text{O})\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$, where $\text{R}=\text{Me}, \text{R}'=\text{Et}, \text{R}=\text{Et}, \text{R}'=\text{Et}$; (iii) $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{R}'\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$, where $\text{R}=\text{Et}, \text{R}'=\text{Et}, \text{R}=\text{Et}, \text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i, \text{R}=\text{Bu}^n, \text{R}'=\text{Pr}^n, \text{R}=\text{Ph}, \text{R}'=\text{Pr}^n, \text{R}=\text{Ph}, \text{R}'=\text{Pr}^i$; and (iv) $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot (\text{R}'\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$, where $\text{R}=\text{Me}, \text{R}'=\text{Me}, \text{R}=\text{Et}, \text{R}'=\text{Me}, \text{R}=\text{Bu}^n, \text{R}'=\text{Pr}^n$.

The adducts formed are colourless transparent liquids which decomposed on heating under reduced pressure. The viscosity of these complexes appears to increase with time at ambient temperature.

On heating the adducts of the type $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$, neat or in benzene solution, they were converted into white glassy solids via elimination of hydrogen chloride, and were insoluble in polar and nonpolar solvents.

The reactions of trialkyl and -dialkyltin chlorides with dialkyl phosphonates were not as exothermic as those with tin tetrachloride. The former form only 1:1 and the latter both 1:1 and 1:2 adducts, which shows higher thermal stability ($\sim 160^\circ$) either neat or in benzene solution. The reactions between diphenyltin dichloride and dialkyl phosphonates appear to be much more exothermic than the corresponding reactions of dialkyltin chlorides. These adducts do not evolve hydrogen chloride in refluxing benzene. The decrease in the acceptor strength of the organotin moiety also decreases the ionicity of both P–H and Sn–Cl bond, thus inhibiting evolution of hydrogen chloride gas.

In all the addition complexes, the coordination of the phosphonate ligand to tin appears to occur

through a phosphoryl oxygen, $(\text{RO})_2\text{P}=\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Sn} \begin{array}{l} / \\ | \\ \backslash \end{array}$

as depicted by a detailed study of their spectroscopic data.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND IR DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ν_{\max}			
	Sn	Cl	P-H	P=O	(P)-O-C	P-O-(C)
SnCl ₄ .2(MeO) ₂ P(O)H	23.80 (24.69)	28.99 (29.45)	2 460	1 187	1 130-950	820
SnCl ₄ .2(EtO) ₂ P(O)H	21.87 (22.19)	26.28 (24.45)	2 455	1 145	1 120-950	780
SnCl ₄ .2(Pr ⁿ O) ₂ P(O)H	19.58 (20.02)	24.09 (24.28)	2 450	1 178	1 100-920	760
SnCl ₄ .2(Pr ⁱ O) ₂ P(O)H	19.63 (20.02)	23.10 (23.95)	2 455	1 175	1 080-900	750
Me ₃ SnCl ₂ .(EtO) ₂ P(O)H	32.87 (33.18)	19.44 (19.84)	2 440	1 185	1 110-910	765
Et ₂ SnCl ₂ .(EtO) ₂ P(O)H	30.58 (30.77)	18.29 (18.40)	2 430	1 200	1 105-920	770
Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2(EtO) ₂ P(O)H	23.61 (23.94)	14.15 (14.32)	2 450	1 180	1 100-910	760
Et ₂ SnCl ₂ .2(EtO) ₂ P(O)H	21.88 (22.66)	13.40 (13.55)	2 425	1 220	1 130-910	780
Et ₂ SnCl ₂ .2(Pr ⁱ O) ₂ P(O)H	20.01 (20.04)	12.19 (12.22)	2 415	1 253	1 085-915	770
Bu ₂ ⁿ SnCl ₂ .2(Pr ⁿ O) ₂ P(O)H	18.54 (18.67)	10.90 (11.16)	2 420	1 230	1 080-920	780
Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2(Pr ⁿ O) ₂ P(O)H	17.23 (17.53)	10.31 (10.50)	2 445	1 198	1 110-940, 915s	845
Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2(Pr ⁱ O) ₂ P(O)H	17.38 (17.58)	9.99 (10.50)	2 440	1 185	1 085-915	895
Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .(MeO) ₂ P(O)H	38.18 (38.38)	10.96 (11.48)	2 445	1 170	1 070-900	745
Et ₂ SnCl ₂ .(MeO) ₂ P(O)H	33.36 (33.79)	9.85 (10.10)	2 430	1 240	1 070-915	770
Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl (Pr ⁿ O) ₂ P(O)H	24.11 (24.36)	7.07 (7.28)	2.420	1 245	1 075-930	775

Ir spectra: Ir spectra of the adducts SnCl₄.2(RO)₂P(O)H (where R=Me, Et, n-Pr, i-Pr) show red-shift (by 25-35 cm⁻¹) of ν_{P-H} stretching vibration (Table 1). The sharp and strong $\nu_{P=O}$ band (1 250-1 280 cm⁻¹) in the free ligand (R'O)₂P(O)H, shifted towards lower wave numbers (~100 cm⁻¹) in the adducts SnCl₄.2L, and appeared in the form of a weak broad band. It is probably coupled in varying degrees with $\nu_{(P)-O-C}$ and $\nu_{P-O-(C)}$ vibrations also.

Ir spectra of the adducts R_nSnCl_{4-n}.m(R'O)₂P(O)H (m=1 or 2) also show shifting of both ν_{P-H} and $\nu_{P=O}$ stretching vibrations. The phosphoryl (P=O) band in these adducts blue-shifted (by 12-80 cm⁻¹) in the form of a sharp and strong band (Table 1). The extent of shifting of the phosphoryl frequency towards lower wave numbers appears to be governed markedly by the nature of groups present on tin and phosphorus. On the basis of ir frequency change (both ν_{P-H} and $\nu_{P=O}$), it is concluded that dimethyl phosphonate is the best donor amongst the dialkyl phosphonates.

Nmr (¹H, ³¹P, ¹¹⁹Sn) spectra: ¹H nmr spectra show a downfield shift of the P-H proton signal indicating deshielding of the phosphorus atom. The P-H coupling constant (J 690 Hz) observed in SnCl₄.2(PrⁿO)₂P(O)H is higher in comparison to that observed (J 680 Hz) in the free ligand, (PrⁿO)₂P(O)H. The ¹H nmr spectra show

characteristic resonance of the corresponding alkyl groups present on tin and the alkoxy groups on phosphorus atom. The chemical shift values of a few representative compounds are summarised in Table 2.

³¹P nmr spectral data of only a few representative compounds could be obtained (Table 2). In the proton decoupled spectrum of SnCl₄.2(PrⁿO)₂P(O)H, only a sharp resonance peak was observed at δ 9.19 indicating a high purity of the complex. The comparison of chemical shift values for the complex and the free ligand (δ 6.5) shows a deshielding effect. In the decoupled spectrum of Bu₂ⁿSnCl₂.2(PrⁿO)₂P(O)H, a single sharp resonance peak observed at δ 7.17 splits into two resonance peak in the coupled spectrum with a coupling constant of 703 Hz.

¹¹⁹Sn nmr spectral data of a few addition complexes have been recorded at room temperature in benzene solution. In the proton decoupled spectra of Me₂SnCl₂.(EtO)₂P(O)H, Me₂SnCl₂.2(EtO)₂P(O)H, Me₃SnCl.(MeO)₂P(O)H and Et₂SnCl.(MeO)₂P(O)H only one sharp resonance peak has been observed at δ -16.63, 61.22, 78.79 and 65.95 respectively. A comparison of these chemical shift values with those of the corresponding tri- and diorganotin chlorides indicates increased shielding of the tin atom in the phosphonate complexes as expected for the increase in its

TABLE 2 - NMR (^1H , ^{31}P) SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	^1H	^{31}P
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	3.9 - 4.2 (d, OMe), 7.45 (P-H)	-
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{EtO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	1.11 - 1.5 (sext., Me), 3.74 - 4.15 (sext., CH_2O), 7.36 (s, P-H)	8.91
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{Pr}^n\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	0.8 - 1.1 (t, Me), 1.72 - 2.0 (q, CH_2), 4.2 (q, CH_2O), 7.05 (s, P-H) ($J_{\text{P-H}}$ 690 Hz)	9.21
$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	1.0 - 1.3 (d, Me), 4.7 (m, CHO), 7.2 (s, P-H)	-
$\text{Et}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{EtO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	1.2 - 1.7 (m, EtSn, Me), 4.1 - 4.4 (sext., CH_2O), 7.2 (s, P-H)	7.70
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{Pr}^n\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	0.7 - 1.0 (t, Me), 1.4 - 1.7 (q, CH_2), 3.7 - 4.0 (sext., CH_2O), 7.1 - 7.3, 7.7 - 7.8 (m, Ph-Sn), 6.8 (s, P-H) ($J_{\text{P-H}}$ 690 Hz)	9.44
$\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{Pr}^n\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$		7.17 (de), 19.99, 3.66 ($J_{\text{P-H}}$ 703 Hz)
$\text{Me}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot (\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$		10.20 (de), 19.83, 0.57 ($J_{\text{P-H}}$ 698 Hz)
$\text{Et}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot (\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$		10.90 (de), 20.61, 1.18 ($J_{\text{P-H}}$ 705 Hz)

coordination number. The ^{119}Sn chemical shift of $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ is consistent with the formation of a pentacoordinated tin species.

Interestingly, the ^{119}Sn nmr signal of $\text{Me}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot (\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ appearing at δ 78.79 in benzene at room temperature shifts further upfield in $(\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ as solvent and appears at δ 6.5. This indicates that although the coordination number of tin did not increase to six, there is a fast exchange between the coordinated and free phosphonate molecules when the latter is used as solvent. Similar observations have been reported recently in the addition complexes of diphenyltin dichloride with tri(n-octyl)phosphine oxide⁴.

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